

1 **Lymphocyte antigen regulation by NOD2.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Genetic studies have identified genes contributing to susceptibility to transplant related mortality,
7 suggesting a role for these genes in immunological tolerance. Polymorphisms in the pattern recognition
8 receptor NOD2, in the host and the donor, are correlated with transplantation related mortality and graft
9 versus host disease in bone marrow transplant patients (1-3). We recently described control of
10 tolerogenic cytokine expression by NOD2, including IL-10 and IL-32 (4, 5).

11 Here we measured total transcription in monocytes from healthy humans and humans with Crohn's
12 Disease whose genomes contain mutations in the pattern recognition receptor *NOD2* (7). We also
13 measured total expression in human cells whose genomes were engineered to stably over-express NOD2
14 or a NOD2 mutation found in patients with Crohn's Disease (6). NOD2 controls expression of lymphocyte
15 antigens, and these molecules function in lymphocyte activation.
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Results

We used a cell culture model of heterologous NOD2 expression (HEK293) (7) to study control of Ly antigen expression by wild-type and disease-associated mutant NOD2.

Figure 1: Ly antigen expression is controlled by NOD2.

a. LY6G6F/LY6G6D

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
207457_s_at	1.71E-02	3.3785227	-2.890807	1.5671968	LY6G6F///LY6G6D	1966/54675	96.4

b. LY9

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
210370_s_at	3.50E-02	-2.7845518	-3.619866	-1.1970278	LY9	3534/54675	93.5

c. LY6K

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
223687_s_at	5.17E-02	-2.4782522	-4.012942	-1.7414589	LY6K	4796/54675	91.2

d. LY6G6E

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
221338_at	5.43E-02	-2.4391569	-4.063658	-0.7645808	LY6G6E	4980/54675	90.9

e. LY96

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
206584_at	6.88E-02	-2.2578567	-4.299737	-2.5299649	LY96	6037/54675	89.0

Figure 2: Control of lymphocyte antigen (Ly) expression by a NOD2 mutant (L1007P) expressed in humans with Crohn's Disease is altered.

a. LY6G6E

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
221338_at	4.43E-02	-2.5962118	-3.586838	-0.786496	LY6G6E	2605/54675	95.2

b. LY6G6F/LY6G6D

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
207457_s_at	4.47E-02	2.5884446	-3.595982	0.82532022	LY6G6F///LY6G6D	2623/54675	95.2

c. LY9

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
210370_s_at	7.28E-02	-2.214357	-4.043092	-0.94053857	LY9	4223/54675	92.3

d. LY6G6C

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
207114_at	1.76E-01	1.552113	-4.833289	1.2114894	LY6G6C	10023/54675	83.3

e. LY6K

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
223687_s_at	1.81E-01	-1.5293731	-4.859337	-1.0869783	LY6K	10328/54675	81.1

f. LY6G5C

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
219860_at	1.98E-01	-1.463115	-4.934451	-0.38365411	LY6G5C	11264/54675	79.4

g. LY96

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
206584_at	2.06E-01	-1.4324576	-4.968776	-1.56822687	LY96	11730/54675	78.5

h. LY75

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205668_at	2.31E-01	-1.3453452	-5.064635	-1.4999275	LY75	13103/54675	76.0

Figure 3: Thymic stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) and epithelial stromal interaction 1 (EPSTI1) expression is controlled by NOD2.

a. Control of TSLP expression by wild-type NOD2.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235737_at	4.17E-02	-2.6459879	-3.796605	-0.4976382	TSLP	4042/54675	92.6

b. Control of TSLP expression by NOD2 L1007P is altered (lost compared to wild-type).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235737_at	5.38E-01	0.6559892	-5.686879	0.17889504	TSLP	30061/54675	45.0

c. Control of EPSTI1 by wild-type NOD2.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235276_at	7.31E-02	2.2124352	-4.358998	2.1158536	EPSTI1	6362/54675	88.4

d. Control of ESPTI1 expression by NOD2 L1007P similar to wild-type in a heterologous system.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235276_at	1.69E-01	1.5822823	-4.798537	0.62120787	EPSTI1	9642/54675	82.4

Figure 4: Multiple lymphocyte antigens are silenced in the monocytes of humans with Crohn's Disease.

a. LY6E

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4061	5.40E-08	0.382	5.437771	2.0795636	9988.71	LY6E	68/17330	99.6

b. LY75

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
065	3.59E-05	0.24	4.132564	0.9918226	1494.81	LY75	219/17330	98.7

c. LY86

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9450	1.27E-04	0.289	3.832817	1.1064489	1923.97	LY86	296/17330	98.3

d. LY96

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23643	6.04E-04	0.273	3.429768	0.9370096	2301.67	LY96	427/17330	97.5

e. LY9

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4063	8.47E-03	0.487	2.632902	1.2814536	1174.36	LY9	975/17330	94.4

f. LY6G5B

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
58496	1.49E-02	0.282	-2.433693	-0.687449	466.76	LY6G5B	1221/17330	93.0

g. LY6G5C

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
80741	5.33E-02	0.476	-1.93267	-0.9200688	51.26	LY6G5C	2165/17330	87.5

Figure 5: EPST11 is among the genes whose expression is most significantly silenced in the monocytes of humans with Crohn's Disease when comparing total transcription to that of healthy monocytes.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
94240	1.69E-18	0.187	8.776554	1.6446379	5241.8	EPST11	8/17330	99.95

LY96 is also known as MD-2, which functions as a component of the LPS receptor together with TLR4 (8).

LY6G6D and LY6G6E are encoded for in a region that lies between the genomic coding regions for MHC class I and class II genes known as MHC III (9).

LY86 is a secreted glycoprotein known as MD-1 with described functions in transplant biology (10).

LY75 is a C-type lectin receptor (CLR) that is expressed on some solid tumor types and is being studied as an antibody drug conjugate target (11).

1 LY6E is a viral restriction factor (12).

2 LY9 (also known as CD229) is a SLAM family receptor that regulates development of thymic innate
3 CD8+ memory T cells and invariant natural killer iNKT cells (13).

4 TSLP is a cytokine that regulates Th2 immunity (14, 15).

5 **Figure 6: Lymphocyte antigens function in lymphocyte activation at the immunologic synapse.**

6 We used a systems biologic tool that identifies co-regulated gene products across the
7 transcriptome in a variety of cellular contexts (SEEK) to identify in an unbiased fashion transcriptional
8 partners and predicted functional partners of Ly6E, Ly96, Ly86, Ly75 and Ly9 (16). We identified *CD53*,
9 *CD48*, and *ITGB2* (*CD18*), co-stimulatory molecules that function in lymphocyte activation at the
10 immunologic synapse, as the genes most closely co-regulated with NOD2-regulated lymphocyte antigens
11 Ly6E, Ly96, Ly86, Ly75 and Ly9 across the transcriptome.

19 We queried a protein-protein interaction database to validate a functional interaction between
20 lymphocyte antigens and CD48 and CD53. Protein-protein interaction analysis revealed LY86 is a
21 predicted interaction partner of CD48 and CD53.

22 **Discussion**

23 We described here control of Ly antigen expression by NOD2, and perturbation of its expression in
24 humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. The innate immune pattern recognition
25 receptor NOD2 controlled Ly antigen expression which was altered upon expression of a NOD2 mutant
26 (naturally occurring variant); NOD2 polymorphism is associated with transplant related mortality. We also
27 identified cytokine TSLP and epithelial stromal interaction 1 as NOD2 transcriptional targets. Systems
28 biologic investigation revealed lymphocyte antigens likely function in lymphocyte activation. Together we
describe a role for NOD2 in regulation of multiple members of a family of genes functioning in lymphocyte
activation. In an accompanying manuscript, we demonstrate dysregulation of lymphocyte antigens as a
central component of the solid organ transplant and graft versus host disease gene expression signatures,
together demonstrating NOD2 controls expression of a family of genes that have critical functions in
immunologic tolerance, and that expression of these genes on at least one immune cell type of humans
with Crohn's Disease is imbalanced.

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26 **Methods**

27 We used published microarray and RNA-sequencing data (GSE22611 and GSE69446) (6, 7) to measure
28 total transcription in human cells (HEK293) stably expressing human or mutant (NOD2 L1007P_) NOD2,
and in the monocytes of humans with Crohn's Disease endogenously expressing mutant NOD2. We used
SEEK (16) and STRING (20) for transcriptional co-regulation and protein-protein interaction analysis.